

Amoebicidal and Fungicidal Activity of new Quinazolones*

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THE occurrence of quinazoline nucleus in a number of biologically active alkaloids and synthetic anti-pathogens has led to a wider search in this group of compounds in recent years. Quinazolones have yielded a large number of compounds having a variety of biological activity like hypnotic, anticonvulsant MAO inhibitor¹⁻⁴ etc. Several quinazolones have been synthesized as potential amoebicides^{5,6}. Compounds such as pyridine, pyrimidine and quinoline derivative which may be regarded structurally or bioisosterically related to quinazolines have been found to possess pronounced antifungal activity⁷⁻¹⁵.

We have now synthesized the new quinazolone derivatives and tested them for amoebicidal and fungicidal activity *in vitro*.

Experimental

*Synthesis of 3-barbituryl quinazolone derivatives*¹⁶ :

Prepared from 5-aminobarbituric acid¹⁴ (0.01 mole) and substituted acetantranils¹⁵ (0.01 mole) obtained by known methods on heating. On cooling a jelly, like mass separated out which was recrystallized from appropriate solvent (EtOH).

Compounds thus prepared in 50-65 yield are listed in Table 1.

Methods :

*Determination of amoebicidal activity against Schizopyrenus russelli*¹⁷.

The amoebae of *S. russelli* were grown in monobacterial cultures on non-nutrient agar plates (2.5%

TABLE-1

Compd. No.	X ₁	X	M.P. °C	Amoebicidal activity against <i>S. russelli</i> at 1 : 1000 dilution
1.	H	H	184	-
2.	Cl	H	140	+
3.	Br	H	202	-
4.	CH ₃	H	240	-
5.	I	H	200	-
6.	NO ₂	H	140	±
7.	Cl	Cl	190	-
8.	Br	Br	170	+
9.	I	I	180	±
10.	II	CH ₃	105	-

(-) Negative culture (+) Positive culture (±) Dead and alive amoebae. All the mps were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Compounds correctly analysed for N.

w/v agar ; 0.5% w/v NaCl, pH 6.8-7.0) supplied with a young culture of *Escherichiuocoli* (2-3 day old, grown on nutrient agar stages as food). A dash of fresh *E. coli* was added to freshly harvested amoebae (in 5% saline) to keep the amoebae motile and stretched. One drop of this suspension was taken in each cavities of the cavity slide and to it double the amount of the drug concentration to be tested, (to compensate for the dilution) was added. Slides were incubated in a moist chamber at 25±1° for 24 hr. After 24 hrs the amoebae were once again observed for judging their viability (Table 1).

*Determination of fungicidal activity*¹⁸ :

Six species of fungi were used in the present study. 1. *Aspergillus niger*, 2. *A. terreus*, 3. *A. nidulans*, 4. *Alternaria tenuis*, 5. *Penicillium funiculosum*, 6. *Curvularia lunata*.

Sabouraud's broth (peptone 10.0 gm/litre dextrose 20.0 gm/liter pH 6.0 approx) was used as the test medium. The compound were dissolved in alcohol, 1.0 ml of test solution (100 µg/ml) was added to 1.0 ml of the medium in each tube. Tubes were autoclaved at 15 lbs for 15 minutes, prior to inoculation with suitable species of fungus. After

TABLE-2 SCREENING OF QUINAZOLONES FOR ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY

Compd No.	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>A. terreus</i>	<i>A. nidulans</i>	<i>Alternaria tenuis</i>	<i>Penicillium funiculosum</i>	<i>Curvularia lunata</i>
Control	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++
1.	++	±	+	-	+	+
2.	++	+++	+++	++++	++±	+
3.	-	-	±	+	-	+
4.	++	+++	++	+	++	++
5.	-	-	+	±	±	++
6.	+	+	++	+	++	±
7.	++++	++++	++±	+++	+++	++±
8.	+	+	±	±	+	++
9.	-	+	+	-	±	±
10.	++	++	++±	++±	+++	+++±

++ to ++++ = Good growth, positive utilization and no fungicidal activity.
± to + = Slight growth, slight fungicidal activity.
- = No growth, fungicidal activity

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inoculation, tubes were incubated at $26^{\circ} \pm 2$ for 7 days, and the vegetative growth recorded visually in each case (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

All the synthesized compounds were tested for amoebicidal and fungicidal activities *in vitro*.

Compound Nos. 1,3,4,5,7 and 10 show amoebicidal activity at 1 : 1000 dilution. Compounds No. 6 and 9 show slight amoebicidal activity.

Compound Nos. 3,5 and 9 show good fungicidal activity and compound Nos. 2,6 and 8 show slight fungicidal activity.

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Fractionation of Atactic Polymethyl Methacrylate by thin Layer Chromatography

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THE purpose of this study is to utilise TLC to explore the possibility of fractionation¹⁻⁴ of

atactic polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) by selecting suitable solvents and to find out the relations with the rate of flow. Polymers of methyl methacrylate have been prepared by photopolymerisation with ultraviolet light without adding photo-sensitizer in bulk at 40° . The product was fractionated by fractional precipitation using acetone and methanol at room temperature ($23 \pm 2^{\circ}$). The intrinsic viscosity of polymer samples was determined in the acetone at $30 \pm 0.1^{\circ}$, using Ostwald viscometer. The average molecular weights (\bar{M}_v) were estimated by using the relation $[\eta] = 6.4 \times 10^{-5} \bar{M}_v^{0.718}$. Similarly number average molecular weights (\bar{M}_n) were calculated by the relation $[\eta] = 7.7 \times 10^{-5} \bar{M}_n^{0.708}$.

Thin layer chromatography has been done in the glass cylinders using $1\frac{1}{2}'' \times 6''$ and $2'' \times 6''$ plates. Silica gel G (E. Merck) of 0.25 mm thickness was used as the stationary phase. The gel layer was activated by heating at 110° for 1 hr. just before use. 0.3% Solution of the samples were prepared separately in the acetone and each of the 15 samples were charged on the stationary phase. Single solvent as well as binary mixtures of acetone, benzene and chloroform were used as developers. The spots were detected by spraying 1% solution of iodine in methanol or 3% solution of potassium permanganate in sulphuric acid.

Four fractions of narrow molecular weights have been selected for this study. Characterization of these fractions is shown in Table-1. The ratio \bar{M}_v/\bar{M}_n for these fractions is very near to unity which shows the close proximity of molecular chain. Preliminary TLC experiments with good solvents like acetone, benzene and chloroform showed that the spots remained immobile in benzene and chloroform whereas movement has been observed with acetone. In this case, the spot moved upto the solvent front. This seems to indicate that the better solubility is not the criteria for spot's mobility and the results obtained suggest that the binary mixture of acetone-benzene or acetone-chloroform may be a suitable developer for resolution.

TABLE-1 CHARACTERISTICS OF ATACTIC METHYL METHACRYLATE POLYMER

Samples	$\bar{M}_v \times 10^{-5}$	$\bar{M}_n \times 10^{-5}$	\bar{M}_v/\bar{M}_n
PMMA-I	5.40	4.99	1.09
PMMA-II	13.87	13.04	1.06
PMMA-III	15.92	14.87	1.07
PMMA-IV	22.85	21.62	1.05

Binary mixtures of acetone and benzene in different proportions were prepared and subjected for development of PMMA samples. The R_f which was zero when acetone concentration is zero, went up steeply to 0.94 at $V > 0.6$, where V is volume fraction. The steep change in R_f value at $V > 0.6$, suggests that at concentration of acetone $V < 0.6$, benzene dominates in the migration of the spot and as soon as the concentration of acetone reaches $V > 0.6$ an adsorption-desorption mechanism becomes operative.

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